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Right way, wrong way, better way
A global model for engineers working with Indigenous communities

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INTRODUCTION

For eight years, a team of Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal staff at the University of South Australia (UniSA) have embedded Aboriginal content across a STEM-based Division. In 2016, a group of Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal women developed, and then piloted, a 'digital extension' of this approach with the *'Blue Wren' STEM, Cultural Understanding and Aboriginal Communities* [1] portal. The centrepiece of this portal is the *Blue Wren Sports Association* problem-based learning collection of vignettes.

The profession of engineering intersects with Aboriginal Australians in many ways. Engineering in remote areas often imposes 'whitefella' (non-Aboriginal) solutions which can mean the difference between improving quality of life (where consultation is done well) or imposing irrelevant, costly and unsustainable solutions (where consultation may have been done poorly) [For example 2].

In Adelaide, South Australia, engineering works proliferate along the banks of its River Torrens (Karrawirra Pari). They include a weir; a hospital; an entertainment precinct; sewers; storm water run-off; a sports oval; a railway; floating barrages; pathways and footbridges. Until recently, most have been developed *without* consultation with the local Kaurna custodians, despite the river's historical, cultural and life-giving role as a food source and gathering place.

This lack of due regard is unsurprising, given historical attempts by Governments to marginalise Aboriginal voices through 'White Australia' policies – displacement from land and stolen generations. A 'cult of forgetfulness practised on a national scale' has denied past wrongs and custodianship of country [3].

By the time an engineering student arrives at university, they have received relatively little by way of education about Australia's First Nations people [4]. This omission in formal learning is mirrored in other countries. For example, where 87% of textbook references to Native Americans pre-date the 1900s [5].

At UniSA a recent survey of engineering students (n26) associated with the study presented, found 73% cited most of their learning was derived from sources other than high school. They demonstrated a superficial or inaccurate understanding such as 'They [Aboriginal people] are not interested in making friends with non-Aboriginal people' to 'They have brown skin' to 'They play diggeridoos'.

As engineering educators, it behoves us to develop graduates who can implement solutions with full and informed community consultation and 'work *with* communities instead of *unto*' [6]. This obligation is globally linked to the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples [7], and mirrored by the Australian professional accrediting body, Engineers Australia [8] and the Reconciliation Action Plans of Engineering firms [for example 9].

This paper presents an evaluation of the first implementation of the *Blue Wren* resource. The pilot took place in a core undergraduate course, *Sustainable Engineering Practice* and examines qualitative changes in student perceptions of working with Aboriginal Australians through looking at student writing.

1 ABORIGINAL CONTENT IN UNDERGRADUATE PROGRAMS (ACUP)

The *Blue Wren* portal is an extension of the Aboriginal Content in Undergraduate Programs (ACUP) project in the Division of Information Technology Engineering and the Environment (ITEE). Most programs in ITEE (including Engineering) are taught at its Mawson Lakes campus. The student population comprises mostly young, predominantly non-Aboriginal, school-leaving males, as well as many international students. Aboriginal lecturers and tutors work with students and staff to develop cultural sensitivity; consultation skills and social responsibility when working with Aboriginal communities. The approach taps into the preferred practical learning styles of STEM students often through case studies [10]. Content is embedded within an existing course and links closely to course objectives and assessment.

In 2017 the *Blue Wren* portal was created by the working group in response to UniSA's Digital Learning Strategy. The resource was developed not so much to fill a gap, but expand on an approach which had already gained national recognition.

2 THE BLUE WREN PORTAL

The working group which developed the *Blue Wren* portal comprises seven women – three Aboriginal and four who are non-Aboriginal. Consulting to the group were Aboriginal Elders; engineering students past and present and a former student and practising senior engineer from large engineering firm, WSP.

The portal provides an array of discipline specific resources including piece-to-camera testimonials from Aboriginal Elders and Faculty, research e-readers, and the centrepiece *Blue Wren Aboriginal Sporting Association* vignettes (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Screenshot Blue Wren Online Resource

2.1 Blue Wren Aboriginal Sporting Association case study vignettes

The four sequential vignettes (written primarily by the Aboriginal members of the working group) encourage students to identify interactions between the consulting engineer (James) and the Sports Association Committee (chaired by Eddie):

When Uncle George comes to visit the Blue Wren Sporting Association he finds it difficult to get down the ramp or access any part of the facility. He instructs the Chairperson, Eddie, to sort out the problem. Eddie invites senior engineer, James, to work with the Association to fix the facilities. However, James (who thinks he has all the answers) soon finds out he has a LOT of learning to do.

Prior to each vignette students are given guided questions to consider while watching the video. Such as 'What are the hallmarks of a good engineer?', 'How can James be more inclusive?', 'Where does technical jargon belong?'

3 METHODOLOGY

The *Blue Wren* portal was piloted in the first year engineering course *Sustainable Engineering Practice (SEP)* in Semester 2 2017 and Semester 1 2018. This course introduces students to the engineering profession and how it is practised within a 'sustainable' context. Students learn about their possible future roles, the work environment, professional attributes of engineers, engineering ethics and sustainability.

SEP includes two lectures – both delivered by Aboriginal staff - focused on cultural and community consultation. One is about Aboriginal history and culture and the second guides the students through the *Blue Wren* vignettes. The students then participate in a culture forum with Aboriginal tutors to explore their own perceptions

about culture and how these link to the profession of engineering. They apply this learning to write a report with assistance from a selection of case studies and other resources via the *Blue Wren* portal. Finally, students apply their learning to develop culturally appropriate solutions to the Engineers Without Borders Humanitarian Challenge – their capstone assignment.

In order to investigate improvements in the quality of student understanding we looked at the depth of student response in their ‘culture forum’. We also examined the quality of their references to Aboriginal Australians in their reports prior to and following the implementation of the *Blue Wren*.

4 RESULTS

The samples of student work chosen are indicative of our observations overall.

4.1 The culture forum

In order to investigate improvements in the quality of student understanding we looked at the depth of student response in their ‘culture forum’. Here, the students explored definitions of culture; engineering and Aboriginal Australians in contemporary society; linkages to their Engineers Without Borders task and what they would take into professional life following their interaction with the *Blue Wren* vignettes.

Prior to the introduction of the *Blue Wren* portal and vignettes (*SEP*, Semester 1 2017) students showed good general understanding of cultural diversity and its importance. However, when asked ‘What would you take into your professional life with regard to culture, Aboriginal Australians and professional practice’ they often used language of an ‘othering’ nature including ‘us’ and ‘them’.

Following the introduction of the *Blue Wren* vignettes (*SEP*, Semester 1 2018), students made clear references to how their knowledge of community engagement and consultation impacted on their professional conduct. They translated abstract concepts into well-articulated changes in their thinking:

...[Being new to Australia] I thought this course was totally irrelevant for a future engineer like me...But...I learned more about Indigenous people, how they were oppressed and deprived of basic human rights...That knowledge has helped me respect and empathise not only with Aboriginal culture, but with all the different cultures that I will have to encounter... Student A

Student A continues to reflect on the impact the *Blue Wren* vignettes:

The previous me was more like the ignorant "James" in the first 2 videos of the Blue Wren Series, who would force opinions and beliefs on people without considering their thoughts, but this course: the lectures, the videos, made me reflect and question myself - would I really be able to become a good engineer or a good person in general and help people if I be like this? Student A

Student A then applies learning to professional conduct in a diverse setting:

This really helped me to see the world in a different angle. I know now that in order to give a good suggestion or develop a solution that actually works, I need to know about the cultural views, beliefs and opinions of the people that I am working with, because no two cultures are the same and what I think is appropriate might not be appropriate for others. Student A

Student B (SEP, Semester 1 2018) refers specifically to the inappropriate actions of “James” the engineer and reflects on how these should be avoided in professional conduct.

Engineers should always put people first and that is through listening. Listening indicates concentration, respect and moreover humility. ...Professional jargon should be eliminated or made clear to the community. In the Blue Wren Aboriginal Sports Association series 'James' uses professional terminologies to interact with the Indigenous community, which of course did not make sense to them. Student B

The *Blue Wren* vignettes focus on the importance of acknowledgement of traditional owners and sensitivity when working on Aboriginal land. Students’ depth of understanding of Australian culture and connection to land is a recurrent theme in forum responses and a notable development in student insight since the introduction of the *Blue Wren* portal. Student C (SEP, Semester 1 2018) makes reference to respecting the fact that all of Australia is Aboriginal Australia.

Australian engineering is bound to intersect with Aboriginal Australians Aboriginal people are the original custodians of the Australian land. ...Every region across Australia has its rightful heritage owners, all with varying cultural behaviours and beliefs. It is compulsory to seek permission from the original custodians of the region before any structural, environmental or physical changes are made...it is the respectful and humane thing to do. Student C

Student D (SEP, Semester 1 2018) similarly reflects on the notion of Aboriginal land ownership across Australia.

I think it is important to always be aware that the Aboriginal Australians are the traditional owners of the land. This ownership extends to the entire country, so any projects will be on Aboriginal owned land. Student D

The above examples link to the impact the *Blue Wren* portal and vignettes have had on student recognition of Aboriginal culture, connection to land and history. Students demonstrated their ability to translate best practice principles such as consultation, communication and professional conduct into tangible behaviours and actions that will transform their ability personally and professionally to engage meaningfully with Aboriginal people and communities in their professional lives as engineers.

4.2 Quality of report assignment

In comparing assignments which achieved the highest mark (High Distinction 85 – 100%), we can see a discernible difference in the depth and quality of the work and clear evidence of how the *Blue Wren* resource has informed this work.

For example, prior to the implementation of the *Blue Wren* resource, assignments made generic comments about areas such as understanding the importance of cultural values; stakeholder needs and the consequences of miscommunication. Following the implementation of *Blue Wren* resource, students drew on the practical examples provided where James showed disrespect through stereotyping (making assumptions the Sports Association was ‘Government funded’) or ignored the opinions of the Aboriginal members of the Sports Association deferring, instead, to the one person he did not view as Aboriginal. Students observed how the client felt neglected and how solutions would be less appropriate as a result.

Even the lower assessed assignments, when compared, showed more depth of insight. For example, assignments achieving between 50 and 55% mentioned how the resource exemplified disrespect toward a junior employee of the engineering firm of Brazilian origin (Pablo) who tended to be ignored and cut off during conversations.

Thus, there was clear integration of the many principals presented in the resource and the teaching team felt confident students demonstrated an understanding of the interactions between engineering and people in the social, cultural, environmental contexts in which they operate.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In a world where the voices of First Nations people are often silenced, the *Blue Wren* approach signifies how we can work together to change the next generation of engineers.

A collaborative teaching innovation led by Aboriginal staff with faculty, students and practising engineers provides a holistic and inclusive approach. As the examples demonstrate, not only has due respect been demonstrated for our First Australians, the pedagogical and professional requirements have also been met.

Despite the paucity of student prior learning and understanding about Aboriginal Australians, the *Blue Wren* vignettes have appeared meaningfully and thoughtfully throughout student work. The open-source resource will remain accessible to students throughout their studies and into their careers as engineers.

Reconciliation work remains difficult – political views; values and lived experiences are often strongly skewed towards ‘righteousness’ and ‘wrongfulness’. A better way is to work collaboratively towards an end point which acknowledges differences but celebrates our common aspirations as colleagues and teachers. The approach must incorporate the cultural leadership of Aboriginal people, while integrating pedagogical relevance and effectiveness from engineering staff. The work presented here provides

a model of Reconciliation-in-action – Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal staff working together to create strong links to ethical practice for our burgeoning engineers.

'Remember - We are all learning.' (Uncle George, Aboriginal Elder, Blue Wren Sporting Association).

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REFERENCES

- [1] University of South Australia (2017) *Stem, cultural understanding and Aboriginal communities*, University of South Australia.
- [2] Uniting Communities (2011) *APY Lands: Sun farm at Umuwa* The Anangu Lands Paper Tracker.
- [3] Stanner, WEH (1969) *The Boyer Lectures 1968 – After the Dreaming* Australian Broadcasting Commission, Sydney.
- [4] Harrison, N, Greenfield, M (2011) Relationship to place: positioning Aboriginal knowledge and perspectives in classroom pedagogies *Critical studies in Education*, Vol. 52 (1), p. 65-76.
- [5] Houska, Tara (2017) 'The Standing Rock resistance and our fight for Indigenous rights' TEDWomen 2017.
- [6] Duff, A, Brodie, T, Furber-Gillick, D, Quinn, D, Smith, E (2011), *Do with and not to. Building cultural understanding, enabling communication and promoting the spirit of reconciliation in first year engineering*, Australasian Association for Engineering Education Conference, Engineers Australia, Perth, pp. 133-139.
- [7] United Nations (2008) *United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples*.
- [8] Engineers Australia (2018), *Our Code of Ethics* Australia.
- [9] WSP (2016) *WSP 2016 – 2018 Reconciliation Action Plan*, Australia.
- [10] Savage, N., Birch, R., Noussi, E. (2011) *Motivation of engineering students in higher education* *Engineering Education*, Vol. 6 (2) p. 39-46.